

ISic0403

I.Sicily inscription 0403

Language

Latin

Type

Engraved

Material

marble

Object

Statue base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

Lost

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Recovered along with parts of a marble gateway and seven marble statues during work on the city fortifications, c.1530

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Extinctori tyrannicae
2. [foe]ditatis [fun]dat[oriliber]
3. [tatis ---]

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation (en)

To the eliminator of foul tryanny, founder of freedom...

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491614

EDCS 21900444

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7122 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

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